

OCEAN ICE News – August 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to August's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, OCEAN ICE at FRISP 2025, highlighting June's Climate Coffee and a recent OCEAN ICE publication. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in August, September, October and November. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in September!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Petra Langebroek

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Petra Langebroek, Research Director at NORCE.

Read the feature on Petra [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE at FRISP 2025

Shenjie Zhou and Yixi Zheng both represented OCEAN ICE at FRISP 2025, held in Rovaniemi, Finland.

Shenjie: Two unique datasets were presented at FRISP, developed with support from OCEAN ICE as part of WP1. The first dataset is the inaugural pan-Antarctic compilation of mooring time series, consisting of 521 records from 470 mooring sites across the continental shelf, shelf break, and under-ice shelf regions around Antarctica. Energy spectral analysis reveals dominant tidal motions at semi-diurnal, diurnal, and fortnightly frequencies, along with strong non-tidal variability at timescales longer than synoptic.

Yixi: Antarctic ice shelves are losing mass rapidly, primarily due to oceanic melting, introducing significant uncertainties in future sea-level projection. The melt rate of ice shelves largely controlled by the turbulent transfer of heat within the ice-ocean boundary layer, a process yet poorly understood due to limited observations. During 2023-2024 season, we deployed two mooring strings beneath the Fimbul Ice Shelf, positioned above a basal channel, and obtained a year-long time series of key ocean properties.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – June

Catch up on June's Climate Coffee with Pietro Viglino: Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, Drawing on OCEAN ICE experience [here](#).

What this webinar is about: The Horizon Europe-funded project OCEAN ICE adheres to open science practices and supports the publication of complementary materials that facilitate the reuse of the project's data. One key tool is the OCEAN ICE literacy portal, which provides instructions and examples about creating new research products using Jupyter Notebooks, which are openly available for testing and further use. In this talk, after a short introduction about how to interact with OCEAN ICE's data service (ERDDAP) using Python, the participants will be guided through the exploration of these data and their visualization in a Jupyter environment. In this way, the participants will obtain the tools to play with code using the same data typology that is used in the Notebooks available in open access for the OCEAN ICE project.

12 June 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Pietro Viglino (ETT)

**Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement
them, drawing on the experience in the
OCEAN ICE project**

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE Publication - Bathymetry-Constrained Warm-Mode Melt Estimates Derived From Analysing Oceanic Gateways in Antarctica

A paper featuring Torsten Albrecht from OCEAN ICE was published recently. Please find a short summary of the paper below.

In the new paper, the authors identify potential oceanic gateways to Antarctic grounding lines based on high-resolution bathymetry data and examine the effect of access depths on ice-shelf melt rates. The identified gateways manifest the deepest topographic features that could channel warm water masses to the base of the ice sheet. They find oceanic gateways in several Antarctic regions and estimate an upper bound of melt rate changes in case warm water masses at intermediate depth gain access to the ice shelf cavities.

Read the full paper [here](#).

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in August, September, October and November, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Amina Ben Salah on A Copula-Based Approach to Explore Climate-Driven Ocean Variability In the Gibraltar Strait.

28 August 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

28 August 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Amina Ben Salah (UAE)

A Copula-Based Approach to Explore
Climate-Driven Ocean Variability in the
Strait of Gibraltar

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

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the European Union

Climate Coffee with Audrey Minière on Estimating ocean warming: Challenges & recommendations for robust assessment

25 September 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

25 September 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Audrey Minière (ENS)

Estimating ocean warming: challenges
and recommendations for robust
assessment

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Climate Coffee with Blanca Fernández Álvarez on How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean MHW

30 October 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

30 October 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Blanca Fernández-Álvarez (IMEDEA-CSIC)

How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine Heatwaves

Climate Coffee with Natacha Legrix De La Salle on Surface and Subsurface Compound MHW and Biogeochemical Extremes

Under Climate Change.

27 November 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

27 November 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET

Online

Natacha Legrix De La Salle (Univ. Liverpool)

Surface and Subsurface Compound Marine Heatwave and Biogeochemical Extremes Under Climate Change

Save the Date: 15-17 September 2025 – OCEAN ICE Annual Project Meeting, Copenhagen

Save the dates for the OCEAN ICE Annual Project Meeting, 15-17 September 2025, which will be kindly hosted by the Danish Meteorological Institute in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 15-17th September 2025, OCEAN ICE Annual Project meeting, Copenhagen, Denmark
- 25th-26th September, The All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA), Brussels, Belgium

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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www.ocean-ice.eu

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https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

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Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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